

ISic0797

I.Sicily inscription 0797

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θ(εοῖς) κ(αταχθονίοις)
2. Μ(άρκος) · Ἀκύλιος
3. Αἰλιανὸς · ἔ
4. ζησεν ἔτη
5. μ · σύμβιος
6. ἀνδρὶ εὐσεβεῖ

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644899

EDR 140745

EDCS 41300107

PHI 175748

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1975.0457

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 143

Ferrua, A 1941. Analecta sicula. *Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 267 no.38

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